

Editorial

A Manifesto from the Margins: A New Epoch for (Non)Theoretical Mathematics Education Research

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The Journal

ABSTRACT: This editorial, introducing the *Journal for Theoretical & Marginal Mathematics Education*, is historically situated in a moment when the field of mathematics education research is on the precipice of acknowledging that the old world is dying. That is to say, the way research has been done before is no longer adequate for operating within the White, Colonial, cis-hetero Patriarchal, Abled Capitalist dystopia we find ourselves. This inadequacy is, however, not a reason for despair but instead for celebration. Instead of directing our resources towards reifying existing norms and structures, towards adopting exhausted methods and theories—as is the way of the old world—we can instead foster a ‘new aesthetics’ of mathematics education research, wherein we remake the very material that constitutes mathematics education research itself. In doing so, we engage with the politics of the margins of mathematics education research. We discuss the critical, philosophical, and psychoanalytic as three potential, but non-exhaustive, departures from mathematics education research as it has been. Each of these marginal approaches, in their own way, points to the ways that presuming a fixed mathematics education research enacts exclusionary politics and precludes change. Let this be our manifesto, written from the margins, for a more root-grasping, more self-reflective, and freer mathematics education research.

KEYWORDS: *mathematics education; critique; philosophy; psychoanalysis; publishing*

The old world is dying, and the new world struggles to be born
as monsters emerge to roam the chiaroscuro twilight.

—Antonio Gramsci (1983), *Prison Notebooks*

The old world *is* dying. There is a growing recognition in *mathematics education* that the way things have been done before is no longer adequate (e.g., Gutiérrez, 2013, 2022; Martin, 2021), if indeed it ever was. In this critical moment of pandemic, pareidolia, post-factualism, climate

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catastrophe, polysemy disavowal, and global (White, Colonial, cis-hetero Patriarchal, Abled) Capitalist dystopia, this conclusion is perhaps inevitable—even if one discounts the trail of bodies that *mathematics education* has left metaphorically and literally in its wake (Andrade-Molina, 2021; Bowers, 2021b; Parra, 2021). The old world is dying—but weep not, friend, for this is not an invitation to despair but instead to rebirth:

If there is [a hell], it is what is already here, the hell we live in every day, that we make by being together. There are two ways to escape suffering it. The first is easy for many: accept the hell, and become such a part of it that you can no longer see it. The second is risky and demands constant vigilance and apprehension: seek and learn to recognize who and what, in the midst of hell, are not hell, then make them endure, give them space. (Calvino, 1978, as cited in Parra, 2021, p. 78)

We, as a field, have the choice to direct our resources (time, attention—i.e., research) towards either reifying existing norms and structures or towards fostering a new aesthetics of mathematics education research (Dubbs, 2021). Now, then, is our moment: the moment to throw off the shackles of old violences (e.g., Andrade-Molina, 2021; Chronaki et al., 2022; Martin et al., 2019; Pais, 2012)! Let us embrace the power we have always had but rarely used, the power to define our role and purpose, the power to “develop a revolt, a rebellion, ... the stubbornness of doing something that is doomed to fail, of doing what is needed to do, or of doing what we are required to do in order to find/build meaning to our path” (Parra, 2021, p. 78).

We stand on the brink of opportunity, yet the new world struggles to be born—monsters roam the twilight, primeval ghosts of hegemony loath to relinquish power. Some of these monsters bear the garb of our institutions, some of our ideologies, and others wear the faces of (often well-intentioned) people. There is a commonplace pursuit of the appearance of change without the actual substance of change, leaving marginalized researchers (and their constituent research) with a Catch-22: develop a research agenda that sincerely reflects their marginalized being (e.g., through marginalized axiologies and onto-epistemologies) and face summary exclusion and ejection from institutions of *mathematics education*, or leave so much of themselves behind in the quest for survival that they become no more than the phantasmic echoes of themselves (Bowers, in press; Brown & Leigh, 2018; Turner, 2003). Repeatedly, we have seen important emerging researchers and perspectives ejected from spaces of mathematics education for refusing to change that same thing which makes them important. Concurrently, others are ushered through exactly because of how harmless their contribution is to the violent status quo. Perennially, we see the same exclusionary principles rehashed in different form (e.g., Heid, 2010; NCTM, 2014) and summarily refuted (e.g., Martin, 2015; Martin et al., 2010).⁴ Time and time again, we have seen exclusionary institutional practices interrogated, but left substantively unchanged (Waid, 2022). The time for refusal is, and has been, here.

Role of the *Journal*

Welcome to the inaugural issue of the *Journal for Theoretical & Marginal Mathematics Education* (*JTM-ME*; the *Journal*). This is a vanguard outlet, or what anarchists would call a locus of Direct Action, that attempts to answer the accusatory questions such as “Is this mathematics education [research]?” and “Where’s the math?” from outside the boundaries imposed by hegemony.

⁴ One may note the added layer of frustration we are communicating in our choice of references here—it is inevitably left to marginalized people to rehash different versions of the same fight over and over again, *ad nauseum*. Often, as in the cited cases, this relates partially or wholly to some version of the hegemonic contention that person(s) or institution(s) *can* be apolitical. This contention is, quite simply, false—because of ideology.

Questions such as this, we argue, are antagonistic disavowals of polysemy (see Bowers, 2021a; Cabral & Baldino, 2022; Shah, 2019) that immediately⁵ pass the crucial bifurcation point of conceptualizing the field—past “what *is* mathematics education? what is *in*? what is *out*? what is *not* mathematics education?”—where these questions at first seem to operate. Instead, this polysemic disavowal, and therefore these questions, attempt to foreclose a political agenda for the field by presuming a monolithic and univocal meaning for “mathematics education.” Despite attempts to rein-in *mathematics*—“the commonsense meaning [of the signifier ‘mathematics’] should not be considered enough to ground [the research field called] mathematics education” (Cabral & Baldino, 2022, p. 1)—and *mathematics education (research)*, the field has not, and does not, have a fixed object of study (Dubbs, 2021).

As a possible response to this attempted foreclosure, and as a way to (re)avow a political agenda for the field, the authors represented in this Volume use critical, philosophical, Indigenous, and other marginalized approaches to reflect on and frame their own experiences in mathematics education, on the teaching and learning of mathematics, and on the field as a whole. In this way, the articles in this Volume represent a subjectivity of mathematics education research authorship that the *Journal* is proud to offer to the field.⁶

The reader may see that the contents of this Volume are quite speculative, leading to questions such as, “How is this research useful?” The answer may very well be, “I don’t know.” However, within the communal spirit of mathematics education which we wish to advance, and the global world in which we all live, continued reflection on the articles herein (and in future volumes of *JTM-ME*) hopefully lead to reframing one’s thinking and even new ways of thinking what is possible. The Editorial Board and authors represented in this Volume collectively bring to our work high-level, academic reflection on the existential burden of what it means to be a mathematics education researcher or practitioner. Further, we avow this existential reflection as critical for the field as we move further into the 21st Century. Such a shift is anything but new, yet *JTM-ME* seeks to breathe additional and complementary life into what Martin and colleagues (2010) have already observed over a decade ago:

[N]ew scholars have entered the field and turned their attention to equity-oriented and critical scholarship, [and] they have increasingly drawn from theories and methods outside of mathematics education and raised questions that go far beyond issues of content... [M]any of the scholars conducting this research are scholars of color, female, and critical White scholars [... who have...] eschewed tradition. (Martin et al., 2010, p. 16)

We affirm this shift and charge the field with pushing the boundaries even further into the margins, towards a further eschewing of the traditions of the field *qua* unexamined presuppositions about the nature of mathematics, its education, and our research enterprise.

Unexamined presuppositions are a grave threat to our work, ourselves as human beings, and the students and teachers who are the subjects of our research. In this way, while the work offered herein may be billed as “theoretical,” we argue that it is in fact *quite non-theoretical*: the roots of each contribution lay in the lived dissonance of marginal realities *contra* hegemonic presupposition. Here, the authors subsequently make this dissonance concrete and transferable in the form of research artifacts. We hope that these artifacts represent the critical, philosophical, Indigenous, and psychoanalytic spirit of a growing number of researchers and practitioners who are

⁵ “Immediate” in the Hegelian sense, meaning what occurs first, before maturation.

⁶ This effort has seen growing support, often spearheaded by new and emerging researchers, such as in a recent working group at the Psychology of Mathematics Education–North America conference that benefitted from participation by a breadth of established researchers and graduate students (Abreu et al., 2022).

increasingly concerned about the purpose of our field, about the existence of the field in the future, about what harm or good we are collectively doing as a field, and about the imperative to turn to speculative research as the world continues to rocket through and towards an epoch of great disorder and crisis/symptoms.

In this vein, the work collectively represented in this Volume and by the launch of the *Journal* reflects Žižek's (Big Think, 2012) warning that action today is privileged above thinking ("act, but don't think too much"), an ideological commitment *par excellence*. We need thinking, speculation, and reflection today more than ever. It is only from this place that we will be prepared to take action in the field and in the world. It is a fool's errand to constantly tread water for its own sake which does naught to move us beyond the deep, when we might instead pause for a moment and reason that we should make for the shore. The articles in our first issue reflect this necessity of thinking as a precondition for our future actions as a research field.

In many ways, we conceptualize the *Journal* in a similar vein as *Constructivist Foundations*,⁷ *Journal of Humanistic Mathematics*, or *Journal of Urban Mathematics Education*. These are specialty journals with a specifically targeted audience. So, too, is *JTM-ME*. Our specialty happens to be those philosophical, critical, psychoanalytic, indigenious, diasporic, post-qualitative, and experimental perspectives not explicitly captured by these other journals (e.g., the psychoanalytic paradigm does not allow for humanism). Moreover, most journals carry one or another structural restriction that would necessarily constrain futurity against our purpose, such as the short word limit of *For the Learning of Mathematics* which prevents some articles from being published there. It is our contention that the articles we endeavor to publish may require more than 5,000 words to sufficiently develop their arguments; thus, the articles we seek might include those more theoretically or philosophically complex than 5,000 words would allow, or that there is a difference of form that our publications might take (e.g., artistic forms).⁸ In keeping with the aforementioned journals, *JTM-ME* was conceived with a specific target audience in mind—viz. the field of mathematics education researchers. Further, we align our project with the *Mathematics Education and Society* conference and the occurrence of edited books that align with the *Journal's* goals—however, the *Journal* strives to serve as a "bridge" between these periodic occurrences of publication and gathering. By establishing a continuous thread (i.e., we publish on demand using DOIs after peer review and production) for this type of work, we seek to establish this type of work as a regular and foundational source of knowledge for the field.

In what follows in this editorial, each of the leading editors of the *Journal* elaborate, from their respective marginal perspective, their take on the field writ large and on mathematics education research *per se*. None provide prescriptions for mathematics education research. Instead, each editor provides an entrée into thinking of mathematics education research from the margins.

The Critical: Grasping at the Roots of Mathematics Education

(Written by David M. Bowers)

A cluster of related words, including "crisis", "criticism", and "critique", all derive from the Greek verb *krinein*, meaning "to decide" or "to judge". "Crisis" can mean, in general,

⁷ After performing an extensive citation network analysis of the *Journal for Research in Mathematics Education*, *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, and *For the Learning of Mathematics*, the second author, Dubbs (2017, 2021a), concluded that the overarching characterization of those journals, by way of citation analysis, was a fifty-year history of constructivist experiments in teaching and learning.

⁸ Notwithstanding this criterion, *For the Learning of Mathematics (FLM)* has graciously established a reciprocal relationship with us. For example, in the case when submissions exceed their word limit, authors will be given the editorial suggestion of forwarding the manuscript to *JTM-ME*.

“a time of intense difficulty or danger” or, more specifically in a medical context, “the turning point of a disease when an important change takes place indicating either recovery or death”. Likewise, “criticism” has the general meaning of “the expression of disapproval of someone or something based on perceived faults or mistakes” and the more specific meaning of “the critical assessment of a literary or artistic work”. “Critique” means “a detailed analysis and assessment”. The medical meaning of “crisis” also carries the implication of a turning-point where alternative actions are possible. Thus, the diverse connotations of “crisis” refer to dangerous situations and analysis, diagnostic analysis, turning points, and the opportunity for action. Accordingly, we think of “critique” in terms of “critical agency”, signifying that critique refers to both reflection and action, integrating the various aforementioned connotations. (Greer & Skovsmose, 2012, p. 1)

This journal aims to become a home for a diverse collection of mathematics education researchers and their constituent research: Critical, philosophical, psychoanalytic, indigenous, diasporic, post-qualitative, experimental, theoretical, cross-disciplinary, and so forth. To one unfamiliar with the commonplace confluence of these sorts of spaces, this almost definitionally surfaces a question: What is it that ties these superficially disparate areas together and offers a cohesive vision? Why do these belong here, together, and not in a dozen separate journals with separate foci? The truest answer is that these questions, at least in their hegemonic formulation, are irrelevant distractions of the same breed as “where’s the mathematics,” rooted as they are in the same ideological assumptions that we aim to disrupt and unsettle.⁹ There is little to be gained, in our view, from simply re-creating and reifying the sorts of colonial compartmentalization represented in the hegemonic formulation of the question (Fanon, 1961/2005; Patel, 2016). However, within the locus of critical research, there are at least two good reasons to take a moment here to respond to this line of questioning as a wholly sincere thing: (1) Dominant ideology is powerful and inescapable, and it is wholly rational that many readers might legitimately carry this wondering at this moment, and (2) responding to this wondering offers an opportunity to call others *into* our work. With that in mind, and since responding to this line of questioning will allow us to consider the role of criticality within *JTM-ME*, allow me (David) to provide *one* answer which I find personally and professionally meaningful. We allude to one version of this answer in our naming of the journal through the word “marginal,” but here I will expand through an exploration of what it means to *be* a critical researcher (or pedagogue, etc.) *doing* critical work, for in my view it is precisely “criticality” that gives rise to unity *through* (not in spite of) our diversity, and to unity through *theory* in dialectic with *action* (what an anarchist might call *praxis*).

Critical Praxis

To describe a person or their actions (research, pedagogy, etc.) as “critical” is, at its core, a very different sort of classification than is describing them as philosophical, psychoanalytic, indigenous, diasporic, and so forth, despite criticality oft being itself constituted of subsets of each.¹⁰ When we describe a researcher or a research artifact as “critical,” we are not naming a specific locus of investigation (e.g., philosophy as the study of the fundamental nature of knowledge, reality, and

⁹ For example, in a recent conversation with the third author, Moore, he said, “As a psychoanalyst, it’s not even clear to me what this content domain we call ‘mathematics’ might be, in terms of an educational content. It’s rather ambiguous in terms of the psyche. So, that leaves a lot open for me to figure out, concerning what it is that we are even trying to do in this field.”

¹⁰ This likely goes without saying given this section being explicitly rooted in my (David’s) perspective on criticality and its role in *JTM-ME*, but though my definition of critical aligns with many in the movement (e.g. Greer & Skovsmose, 2012), there do exist others who would offer a related but distinct characterization of the movement (e.g., Savich, 2020).

existence; psychoanalysis as the study of the unconscious *contra* the conscious), nor a specific axiological or onto-epistemic origin/lineage (e.g., indigenous, diasporic). Instead, we are naming a particular relationship between research(er) and world, a particular confluence of reflection and action. Critical research is defined by its sociopolitical relationship to, and distance from, violent hegemony. Be it Critical Race Theory, QueerCrit, DisCrit/CripCrit, or any other genre of critical that we might name, critical research is that which is *etic* yet refuses to hide away, that which is constructed as the cultural outsider yet claims its rightful presence. Critical research is research that exists in spite of *and* in opposition to hegemony, and which in so doing must necessarily comprise a dialectic of theory and practice, growing and evolving rhizomatically over time towards emancipatory ends. Phrased as succinctly as possible without entirely losing meaning, critical research is emancipatory, and it centers its emancipatory vision around those hegemonically denied liberation.¹¹

What, then, can this critical dialectic of theory and practice look like? It often begins with a conscious decentering of Hegemony, and recentering of the *etic* (be that our own otherness, or the empathic echoes of those with disparate but related experiences, or something else entirely). In doing Critical Research, we are definitionally at odds with hegemony, but “Often these processes [of hegemony] operate at a level below consciousness; they remain unexamined or even unnoticed, in which case the task at hand is to render them visible and expose them to critique.” (Greer & Mukhopadhyay, 2012) This is a central act in Critical Research, and one which any Critical Researcher will necessarily return to over and over again as they continue the ongoing, rhizomatic process of decentering *what is* and recentering *what could be*. From each (re)noticing, the next task is to take what actions we can to resist the violent status quo and create intentional space for emancipatory futurities. It is this iterative and recursive relationship between thought and action, this dialectic of theory and practice, that defines what anarchists would call *praxis* (Bowers & Lawler, 2020, 2021; Bowers et al., in press), and it is precisely this meeting of liberatory theory and practice which defines the heart of Critical Research.

Critical Praxis and the *JTM-ME*

How, then, is critical *praxis* embedded in the being of *JTM-ME*, and how does it justify the presence of the diverse entries in this first issue in a single publication outlet rather than a dozen separate outlets? I will begin with the former, and use that to describe how we arrived at the latter. First, at the level of *noticing*, we recognize that innumerable structural barriers remain in place at most publication outlets of mathematics education for Critical scholars their constituent contributions, especially when those contributions refuse to concede space to hegemonic ideology in content and/or form (Bowers, 2019; Waid, 2022). Thus, it becomes our goal to disrupt, unsettle, or remove those barriers. Some of these barriers are relatively obvious, and in some sense easy to disrupt: *JTM-ME* is free to authors and completely open-access to readers, it consciously seeks papers Critical in their content, it has the ability to connect critical submissions with appropriately critical peer reviewers, and it encourages the length and form of submissions to be selected so as to best convey what the authors aim to convey as opposed to privileging (for example) forms that convey the aesthetic of objectivity to the exclusion of forms that strive to honestly reckon with

¹¹ Some readers unfamiliar with Critical Research may be wondering if this means that those of heavily privileged positioning are denied entry into Critical Research, or if those of marginal positioning are tautologically doing Critical Research. The answer to both is a resounding *no*. In both cases, Critical Research is defined by the interaction of the research(er) *contra* hegemony. Thus, an abled researcher may still be Critical in their approach to Disability if they decenter Aabledness and recenter alternate ways of being (e.g., neurodiversity), whereas a disabled researcher may easily find themselves doing uncritical research as a byproduct of uninterrogated, internalized ableism. Note that this is not a binary or linear relationship, and that there is no distilled essence of *Critical* that one can eventually arrive at—it is an ongoing, iterative process of decentering hegemony and recentering the margins.

the dialectic of objectivity *contra* subjectivity (Abreu et al., 2022; Bowers, 2019). Other barriers are less obvious, or perhaps so obvious/commonplace that they fade into the background. Take, for example, the standard norms of peer review. These norms are so well-embedded in our ethos and ideology that even when they are questioned, they are only questioned *up-to-a-point*, as in *Educational Studies in Mathematics'* recent editorial (Prediger & Wagner, 2022). In contrast, we have drawn inspiration from outside of mathematics education, and instead adopted *open review* as a humanizing and intellectually rigorous alternative to masked review (though we offer both, for choice oft lies at the center of emancipatory work). This allows the peer review process to take the literal or metaphorical form of an ongoing, liberatory conversation, where each reviewer's goal is to support the author(s) in better conveying the ideas and impressions they wish to convey, rather than the memetic stereotype of masked review wherein the product is pressured towards becoming an amalgamation or average of the distinct papers each reviewer wished had been written instead. By tracking these conversations and developments over time, space is also made (in the afterword) for authors and reviewers to make as transparent as possible whose contributions can be seen in which aspects of the final product. These sorts of practices create space for deeply marginalized research to come to light without first undergoing this stereotypical process of being averaged with hegemony until the written work is rendered sufficiently harmless to the status quo, and further allows this process to take place which is less draining and dehumanizing for the author (and reviewers).

In short, *JTM-ME* engages in critical praxis by strategically positioning itself both within and against mathematics education: it was conceptualized as an outlet to make space for forms of research—and their constituent researchers—directly and tacitly excluded from spaces of mathematics education, and concurrently as a space to directly challenge hegemonies, norms, and un-critiqued discourses in mathematics education, i.e., it simultaneously creates new space within mathematics education and challenges traditional spaces of mathematics education. We consciously and intentionally *noticed* structural barriers to the cultivation of this type of emancipatory space and attempted to *dismantle* what we could. This has allowed us to arrive at this issue, at this specific collection of works which we are honored to bring to the world, unified by their recentering of the margins *contra* hegemony: Important work from established scholars who nonetheless could previously find no publication to house their contribution, alongside work from emerging scholars striving to push the boundaries of the field; work that challenges us to imagine a *mathematics education* where children can dream, where practitioners can co-construct liberatory space, where epistemic violences can be more sincerely surfaced and interrogated; work that challenges what *mathematics education* is and can be, that challenges what questions it is allowed to ask and what the final research product should look like in order to convey what it aims to convey; work that allows marginalized researchers to bring more of their genuine selves and experiences into conversation with *mathematics education per se*; work that marks the beginning of another wave of ongoing change.

Recursive Critical Praxis

I will conclude by directing us again to the iterative/recursive process that is Critical Praxis. We are proud of what we (editors, authors, reviewers, and so forth) have been able to bring into existence here, and we are already looking forward to how this emancipatory vision may yet grow. Those of us bringing *JTM-ME* into being already, in many respects, organize ourselves around collectivist/anarchist organizing principles, and this approach actively encourages ongoing change and growth, as for example by limiting unjustified, coercive hierarchies within our institution. For example, I would be more likely to describe my editorial role as being akin to being a community

or union organizer (roles that I have, and continue, to take on in other areas of my life) as opposed to describing it like a traditional editorial position.

What changes, then, are we looking forward to making as we continue our quest of rhizomatic growth? As before, some of these answers are obvious. For example, though myself and the other current editors represent important trajectories of marginalization in terms of gender/sexuality, the oft-overlooked disability, and our broader attempts to grow in our rejection of Whiteness and Imperialism, we are also nonetheless white residents of the Global North. We are in the early stages of a process (estimated to take around two years from the time of this editorial) that will involve one of the current editors stepping down to make space for someone else who can bring different perspectives/lenses that will support us in our critical and emancipatory work, and we also hope to establish a culture where these sorts of organizing roles are regularly rotated rather than letting them become loci of consolidated power. This periodic rotation of editorial leadership is an intentional part of our plan for the *Journal*.

However, just as before, there are necessarily other answers to the question of how we might change which are less obvious. In the spirit of solidarity and endless rhizomatic growth, we look forward to continuing to become more: More radical, more emancipatory, and more *critical*. We can, as stated purely aspirationally in Bakker, Cai, and Zenger's (2021) exploration of future themes for mathematics education, choose to create norms and institutions that call on us to ask "Where's the social justice," to "develop norms wherein it is considered embarrassing to do 'uncritical' research," wherein it is recognized that "there is no such thing as 'neutral,'" and wherein we "recognize the inherent political nature of all work, [with] norms that acknowledge how superficially 'neutral' work tends to empower the oppressor... We [can] normalize (and expect) the full taking up the philosophical and theoretical underpinnings of all of our work (even work that is not considered 'philosophical')." (p. 12) We can, in short, take seriously the possibility of a better world and our communal power to define *mathematics education* towards its fruition (Parra, 2021).

The Philosophical: A *Freer* Mathematics Education Research

(Written by Christopher H. Dubbs)

The main point is not what [words] explain or express, it is the way in which they stage a scene or they create a commonsense: things that the speaker and those that hear it are invited to share—as a spectacle, a feeling, a phrasing, a mode of intelligibility. (Rancière, 2009b, p. 117)

When you, the reader, see the words "mathematics education" or "mathematics education research" what comes to mind? If you were to say them, what image would you wish to conjure in your hearer's mind? Unfortunately, there is no guarantee for me, the writer, or you, the reader/speaker, that our meanings of these terms will be in agreement. *Disagreement* is "not the conflict between one who says white and another who says black" (Rancière, 1995/1999, p. x) but rather "the conflict between one who says white and another who also says white but does not understand the same thing by it or does not understand that the other is saying the same thing in the name of white-ness" (p. x). To borrow Rancière's words, then, there is (potential) disagreement between different researchers and the image of "mathematics education research" they conjure, either (1) in holding divergent conceptions for mathematics education research or (2) in failing to recognize the "mathematics education research"-ness of what another says. We at *JTM-ME* encourage disagreement, or rather, encourage its authors to introduce the potential for

disagreement by reconfiguring and reconceptualizing mathematics education (research) in the meanings we use, the research we do, or any number of other transgressive actions.

As a result of this dissensual condition, we at *JTM-ME* conceive of mathematics education research in the broadest senses possible. Instead of presuming that we can hold onto “mathematics education research” like a static object of study in our gaze, inspecting it with our loupes until every minute feature is revealed, we conceive of a “mathematics education research” that is instead dynamic. One of my (Christopher) ongoing research projects has been to interrogate the foregrounded assumptions and meanings we hold as a field (e.g., using learner vs. student vs. mathematician to refer to the subjects of mathematics education, Dubbs, 2020a; unpacking the plural meanings of *ethics*, Dubbs, 2020b; and describing the ambient conditions of *Urban* mathematics education research, Dubbs, 2021b), with particular attention paid to how the field has constituted itself *per se* since 1970 (Dubbs, 2021a).

I turn, next, to some of my philosophical interlocutors—viz. Jacques Rancière and Michel Foucault—to frame this discussion of the field of mathematics education research and to outline one path towards instituting a *freer* mathematics education research.

Rancière: On Distributions of the Sensible

I call the distribution of the sensible the system of self-evident facts of sense perception that simultaneously discloses the existence of something in common and the delimitations that define the respective parts and positions within it. A distribution of the sensible therefore establishes at one and the same time something common that is shared and exclusive parts. This apportionment of parts and positions is based on a distribution of spaces, times, and forms of activity that determines the very manner in which something in common lends itself to participation and in what way various individuals have a part in this distribution. (Rancière, 2008/2009a, p. 12)

Rancière’s distribution of the sensible is, to emphasize, “the system of self-evident facts of sense perception that simultaneously discloses the existence of something in common and the delimitations that define the respective parts and positions within it” (Rancière, 2009b, p. 12). In our context, a distribution of the sensible is a set of implicit laws that govern what we can see, say, or do as mathematics education research (the thing in common). It further indicates what is sensible: how the ways of doing, seeing, and saying fit together (parts and positions within it).

We operate within a particular distribution of the sensible whenever we classify what is *inside* and what is *outside* mathematics education research. If the topic is not appropriate (e.g., learning phonemes in a Spanish class), we exclude it. In such cases, the exclusion is less political and more categorical. However, in others it is most definitely political.¹² When journals, researchers, and/or reviewers work to exclude (1) novel foci because they are “irrelevant,” (2) alternative theories because they are “too complex for the space,” (3) divergent methods because they are “unprecedented,” and/or (4) alternative research artifacts (e.g., art or prose as opposed to the structured social science research article) because it is “not research”, they are choosing to reify a particular distribution of the sensible, a particular way of understanding what ‘counts’ as mathematics education research.

Each journal—with its own aim, scope, and (implicit) expectations for topics, acceptable theories and analyses, types of conclusions, etc.—therefore, outlines a particular distribution of the sensible, draws its own lines along which the inclusion/exclusion distinction is made. Since individuals (or collectives) create the research, then, a distribution of the sensible outlines particular

¹² Political in the sense that it is concerned with inclusion and exclusion.

ways of being a mathematics education researcher. A distribution of the sensible is political, then, insofar that it is entangled with issues of (in)equitable inclusion of individuals and their ideas.

How do individual researchers find the freedom to pursue their research that is marginalized by particular distributions of the sensible in operation? We enact a *freer* distribution of the sensible here at *JTM-ME*, one that explicitly aims to include new—or historical—and alternative approaches to mathematics education research. It is in this reclaimed space, relocated from the margins to the center, that researchers might begin to experience *freedom* as mathematics education researchers.

Foucault: On Freedom

My role—and that is too emphatic a word—is to show people that they are much freer than they feel, that people accept as truth, as evidence, some themes which have been built up at a certain moment during history, and that this so-called evidence can be criticized and destroyed...All my analyses are against the idea of universal necessities in human existence. They show the arbitrariness of institutions and show which space of freedom we can still enjoy and how many changes can still be made. (Foucault, 1988, pp. 10–11)

Foucault discussed two perspectives on history: (1) history as a mirror, wherein it shows us our past, and (2) history as a lever, wherein it helps us to change the present. His own approach, however, is the ironic position that sometimes mirrors make the best levers (Fendler, 2010). Foucault showed us that by looking back, it is sometimes easier to imagine alternatives in the present. By presenting historical counterexamples to the present state of things, Foucault could help his readers to see that since things have not always been as they are, there is no reason to assume that they must continue to be as they are.

As documented in the *Math Ed Atlas* (Dubbs, 2021a), mathematics education research has not historically—and does not currently—have a singular, proper or object of study. Instead, the dominant foci, methods, etc. have shifted across time. Therefore, it is useful, then, to think of “mathematics education research” as a concept *in time*. Thinking in time enables us to consider the ways that our conceptions are bound to our temporal histories and present times, never fixed but constantly fluid (Butler & Weed, 2011).

In a similar vein, I/we see it as the role of those publishing in *JTM-ME* to fully realize the implications of the mathematics education research landscape being a fluid concept resulting from historical events. The normative assumptions that we make regarding the research foci we can adopt, the theories we can draw on, the methods of research we can use, instead of being a historical inevitability, gained hegemony through historical chance. If we accept that, then we can discard those normative prescriptions and introduce alternatives with little psychic difficulty. If the dominant methods merely “are” and are not “ought”, then there is no need to indenture ourselves to them at all costs. The norms we presume about the forms our research outputs can take, are not only the result of historical events (research as a citational practice necessarily anchors us to our history as a field) but are, in particular, constraints. These assumptions about what we can sensibly see, say, think, and do in the name of mathematics education research constitute a restrictive distribution of the sensible wherein freedom is limited.

Yet, Foucault’s words remind us that we are “freer than [we] feel” (1988, p. 10) under the constraints implied by the dominant distribution of the sensible. And this freedom occurs in at least two ways. First, within the dominant distribution of the sensible, there are transgressive ways that individuals can operate (this is akin to working within the system). Second, there are alternative distributions of the sensible, freer distributions of the sensible that a research can choose to operate within. The dominant distribution of the sensible is not our destiny but rather is one of the many incident and orthogonal distributions of the sensible one might inhabit. For

example, while the field of mathematics education research has largely operated as though the only methodological paradigms whence we might choose are the quantitative or the qualitative (and increasingly often, mixed), this distinction ignores a third possibility (among countless others): humanities-oriented approaches to research.

Humanities-oriented approaches to research include the constellation of approaches which are adjacent to the humanities: historical, critical, psychoanalytic, arts-based, and/or philosophical. These approaches have a history and institutional support outside of mathematics education research: AERA developed the *Standards for Reporting on Humanities-Oriented Research in AERA Publications* (2009). These sorts of humanities-oriented approaches to research are nonsensical within the dominant distribution of the sensible at operation with the field, but by creating space in *JTM-ME*, we might begin to outline a new distribution of the sensible. In this revised distribution of the sensible, this *freer* distribution of the sensible, any of these alternative approaches to research, as well as longer theoretical essays and philosophical analyses that might not be suitable for other journals, are welcome.

Trajectory: The Politics of The Aesthetics of Mathematics Education Research

The main interest in life and work is to become someone else that you were not in the beginning...What is true for writing and for a love relationship is true also for life. The game is worthwhile insofar as we don't know what will be the end. (Foucault, 1988, p. 10)

The reader will be disappointed if they were hoping I/we would offer a revised and totalizing definition of “mathematics education research.” Establishing a fixed definition¹³ of what mathematics education research is (and can) be would necessarily lead to policing (Rancière, 1995/1999), of ensuring compliance to the given definition. Instead, my aim is to institute and maintain a politics of the aesthetics of “mathematics education research”—of emphasizing a constant reconfiguration of what we can see, say, think, and do in the name of mathematics education research. This goal is political since it concerns whose ideas are in-/excluded and aesthetic as it is concerned with the shaping of mathematics education research. I/we do this in the name of increasing the freedom of mathematics education researchers.

Mathematics education research, as a field, is worthwhile insofar as we continue to change. The instant we draw a line and say, “on this side is mathematics education research and on the other is something else entirely,” we lose the game. As soon as we say, this is and that is not, we are making a claim about what we can see, say, do, and think in the name of mathematics education research, a claim about the *proper* distribution of the sensible. At *JTM-ME*, we are attempting to outline a *freer* distribution of the sensible in which mathematics education researchers can operate.

We cannot know the results of this effort, but therein lies the beauty: the beauty of it all is that we cannot be sure what will happen. We can, however, be sure that things can change. Mathematics education research has not, and does not currently, have a fixed definition. Mathematics education research does not have a fixed, and proper, object of study. But, if history is the study of what has been and philosophy is the study of what can be, Foucault helps us to bridge history and philosophy: since today is tomorrow’s history, enacting alternatives today constitutes the historical chance on which tomorrow’s change depends.

¹³ It is for this reason that we have chosen to place “Marginal” in the title of the journal. As the field of mathematics education research changes across time, the margins will necessarily change. Therefore, the topics to be included in *JTM-ME* will vary across time.

The Psychoanalytic: Whither the Phantasy of Mathematics Education?

(Written by Alexander S. Moore)

This is an editorial, so I shall be a bit more polemical than usual here; further, psychoanalytic language may seem overly obtuse or provocative to the non-psychoanalytic reader. This is because, in psychoanalysis, the linguistic devices of metaphor (principle of selection) and metonymy (principle of combination) are the ways in which we understand language use by a subject; both are types of slippage. In reading what I have written, seemingly *provocative* word choice should be understood as intentionally to *evoke*, with that evocation then being followed by a reflection by the reader (i.e., Why did he say it that way? Why did I respond with a certain feeling?), as is the convention in psychoanalytic literature.

Psychoanalytic literature is conceived of as a statute of statements (declarations), wherein psychoanalytic ideas are conceived of as ideas to be instituted—what Tupinambá (2021) has called the *generic perspective of psychoanalysis*—with these statements then reflected on and elaborated as a way of investigating their possible kernels of truth. In this way, psychoanalytic thinking is generative and expansive. Thus, in what I have written here, my word choice and combination is intentional apropos of provoking the reader to reflect on their own reactions to my metaphoric and metonymic devices: the reader's reactions constitute the reader's indistinct binding-point to me as the writer, opening up joint insights that are new to the world; “how” one should read psychoanalytic literature is to read it “to the letter,” then read it again, think about it, think about it some more—and then slowly, over time, it changes one's thinking from the “inside.” This way of conceiving psychoanalytic thinking holds great potential for research in mathematics education. In addition, there is a *critical perspective of psychoanalysis* (Tupinambá, 2021) that focuses on the subject's universality, which is also of great potential in equity research in our field, as the subject's universality is often foreclosed by local metanarratives of equity (Baldino & Cabral, 2006; Žižek, 2018).^{14,15}

Lacanian Psychoanalysis

Psychoanalysis is a controversial theoretical perspective because of its direct theorization of the “unprovable” unconscious; it has always been (Freud and Jung), and continues to be (Lacan, Klein, Winnicott, etc.). It has, since its beginning, been intertwined with critical thought (e.g., the Freudo-Marxist tradition). For my part, I am a Lacanian. In a 1974 interview, Jacques Lacan described psychoanalysis as:

[N]ot a philosophy... It's not even a faith, and I don't feel like calling it a science. Let's say it's a *practice* and that it deals with *what's wrong*... Psychoanalysis is concerned with symptoms, which are the detectors of the malaise of the civilization in which we live... In psychoanalysis, there are no immediate answers, but only the *long, patient search for 'whys'*—[the 'whys' for the symptoms]. (Lacan, 1974, emphasis added)

¹⁴ It is impossible for me to name individually all of the scholars in our field who have influenced the development of my perspective (for example, Sverker Lundin and Felix Lensing are not cited directly in this section), but I cite some examples of literature that have been perhaps most influential to me in the parentheses of this section, with the hope that the reader will seek out such literature and those papers that are cited in them. I am, in particular, indebted to Alexandre Pais, Tânia Cabral, Roberto Baldino, and Melissa Andrade-Molina for their influence and being interlocutors in my work.

¹⁵ The latter part of this claim is based on Hegelian philosophy and Lacanian psychoanalysis. Identity and alienation are strictly correlative, because no signifier can signify itself. For brevity, I shall not go into details here, but interested readers can refer to Baldino and Cabral (2006), Hegel (2015), and Žižek (2018), for example.

In the 1960s French critical movement, psychoanalysis entered the popular culture by way of Lacan's public seminars. Notwithstanding this cultural significance, the technological advent of the 1980s—today saw a swing away from psychoanalysis towards psychiatry (as medicinal), psychological (as scientific), and cognitive behavioral theory (as clinical) interventions; all three of these are capitalist—for example, how psychiatry has manufactured the myth of identity (Thrul, 2022) in order to stabilize the subject's exploitative relationship to capital—whereas psychoanalysis is socialist—insofar as psychoanalysis's endgame is that everyone becomes analysts themselves (e.g., Tupinambá, 2021).¹⁶ It would appear, over the time of these shifts, as if the public was becoming less interested in speculation such as is afforded by psychoanalysis and its avowal of the unconscious, replaced instead by a general popular interest in deductive and scientific modes of inquiry concurrent with the sentimentalism of modernity's technological advent (for example, see Schuller, 2018). I (Alexander), for one, am a bit nostalgic for these “old days” of the psychoanalytic and critical popular movement.¹⁷ What if we have already reached “peak” mathematics education? We may not need to wait for the material world to “unmake” us and our field; we may—possibly—successfully do it ourselves. Perhaps it is time that the field embrace a backwards motion, an “inverted dream,” and focus on the *reasons for the symptoms* rather than ideologically seeking modes of their treatment (see Pais, 2012). Once we have reckoned with these failures ourselves, we shall have to demand germane influence at the policy level.

Generally speaking, psychoanalysis begins with the assumptions that (1) the unconscious exists, and (2) there is no *a priori* human-being. Thus, psychoanalysis forecloses humanism. Privileging instead the *a priori* social link, psychoanalysis affords a different way of approaching the pedagogical situation, one that is based on the desire of the split-subject,¹⁸ situated, as such, in a material condition. Speculative logic is also privileged (e.g., Hegel, 2015), as psychoanalysis works in contradictions and common-sense ‘inversions’ of what is conscious.¹⁹ For this reason, psychoanalysis is also critical of the notion of free will: we act, but we do not know what we are doing—or maybe we do, but we can believe that we don't (Žižek, 2008b). This approach is potentially rather compatible with the desire-based turn (e.g., Gutiérrez, 2022) and the new materialist approaches (e.g., Abreu, this volume; de Freitas & Sinclair, 2013), notwithstanding the potential for these approaches to further usurp additional surplus-value from students (Pais, 2019) or be rejected from broader political discussions (see Pais, 2013) when conducted within the capitalist²⁰ educational ideology.

The Psychoanalytic-Marxist Axis

In addition to these shifts, I hope to see a further embrace by the field of the study of ideology (e.g., Pais, 2013). Further, when combined with critique of (political) economy (e.g., Pais, 2014), psychoanalysis reveals itself as a potent viewpoint to take in analyzing the modern concerns of education researchers and the paradoxes of school. This combination of theoretical perspectives is underrepresented in mathematics education literature, despite being a well-developed and

¹⁶ This is perhaps why the psychoanalytic paradigm is so controversial within the ideology of the capitalist mode of mathematics education research.

¹⁷ As a quick gloss and recent example, consider that the world economy in late capitalism is tied to the U.S. Dollar and the English language, notwithstanding the fact that the U.S. Dollar went off the gold standard in the 1970s, further alienating us from materiality from the 1980s through today.

¹⁸ The negativity of the subject: the subject is always split, desiring, anxious, alienated. This begins with an experience in early childhood when the baby first recognizes themselves in the mirror for the first time.

¹⁹ In psychoanalytic writing, we must use speculative logic precisely in order to arrest the seductive myth of signifying for understanding: Negation is the only way; don't disavow it! There is only “open” writing (see Lacan, n.d.).

²⁰ A recent conversation with Sofía Abreu affirmed this concern (also see Abreu, 2022).

vibrant intellectual tradition. A common critique of this approach is that all the work is the same, not saying anything new—or the critique is prefaced by a naïve assumption that we have moved beyond modernity into a post-class world. I contend that this is not the case, and this contention of mine is reaffirmed every time I visit a school in the clinical teacher education capacity in which I now work.

The psychoanalytic focus of the journal (one of several foci) is aimed at encouraging more scholars to engage with the ideas of the psyche, class struggle as structuring the global experience, and the symptoms we develop as a result. There is no *a priori* human-being; there is only materiality, there is only the social link, our duties to each other to make life livable. *Contra* this observation, the material labor of subjects engaged in the mathematics education enterprise is done precisely for the purpose of qualifying labor-power and seizing surplus-value via the school credit system (e.g., Baldino & Cabral, 2013, 2015; Cabral & Baldino, 2019).

For this reason, a potent combination of theoretical positions is along the psychoanalytic-Marxist axis, which combine to reveal contradictions in the pursuit of equity research amidst an educational system that has been explicitly designed to *not* be equitable (e.g., Baldino & Cabral, 2006, 2013, 2015, 2018; Pais, 2012). Thus, I contend that ideological criticism is necessary if the continued pursuit of equity research is to be undertaken by researchers. As long as we ideologically delineate education along a success/failure dichotomy, equity research will have no choice but to sublimate²¹ its inherent desire for inequity.

For example, mathematics is codified as belonging to the Symbolic (symptoms are also Symbolic; Žižek, 1989/2008), but in psychic reality, mathematics is much more closely related to the traumatic inverse of the Symbolic: the Real.²² The Real is that-which-resists-being-Symbolized, such as, for example, *that-which-causes-anxiety*.²³ Symptoms often develop in response to encounters with the Real, as a Symbolic overdetermination of the Real encounter so that it may be repressed. I was recently reading a new essay by psychoanalytic queer theorist Calvin Thomas (2023), wherein he asks the poignant question: “What the fuck happened to the Real” (p. 245)?²⁴ Indeed, it is a good question.²⁵

Within the field’s research foci, alienation and anxiety are taken up by many researchers, but at the level of affect rather than the level of the symptom within political economy (also see Pais, 2015). In short, psychoanalysis and Marxist dialectical materialism can rescue equity research from

²¹ Sublimation for Lacan is the process of making something seem more socially acceptable *qua* less ‘ideological.’

²² Mathematics in the M20 (the ‘certain’/‘trustworthy’ formulation of mathematics in the 20th-21st centuries) conception is a psychotic structure (Baldino & Cabral, 2018; Moore, 2022). A psychotic structure is, for Lacan, a failure of the Symbolic that reappears in the Imaginary. As a quick gloss, consider how we use our “seeing” of mathematics to codify our faith in it. The pedagogical situation of mathematics education is thus experienced as a pathological encounter. This leads to a split between pseudo-knowledge and true-knowledge, or in other words, “I want to learn” versus “I want to pass” (see Baldino & Cabral, 1998, 1999). Lacan signified this split with the *matheme* $\$ \diamond a$. The diamond operator represents a dialectic and is, in this *matheme*, the location of desire. In the context of mathematics education research, this *matheme* can be read as: Researchers create the reality they want by their ideological phantasies, and they do so unbeknownst to themselves because of their desire (see Lacan, n.d.). For this reason, in my work, I investigate the relationship of mathematics to the sexual psychic structures, such as mathematics as a procreational proxy *qua* an attempt to reclaim the psychic unity of childhood and avoid the failure of gender to signify sexual difference, the masculine desire to signify, and the search for the Hegelian Absolute as a symptom of the sexual failure in the existential process of becoming-gender-embodied (see Gherovici & Steinkoler, 2023; Jöttkandt, 2016; Lacan, 1975/1998, 2018; Moore, 2022; Žižek, 2020). As a result of these factors, what we end up doing in life is “*much worse*” (see Lacan, 2018).

²³ Even in attempting to signify the Real, I must resort to signifier-amalgams that do not point to anything.

²⁴ For example, the ideology of heteronormativity forecloses the queer accidentality of the Real, which is present nonetheless.

²⁵ To draw on another term from Thomas (2023), perhaps the field needs a “*petit a-bortion*” of its agenda at the present moment.

itself, but only if we are willing to engage with alternatives to the capitalist mode of school (for example, see Leopold, this volume; Pais, 2019). Or, said in ‘other’ words, this approach can help guide us to “desire better” (Cameron More, November 6, 2022, personal communication).²⁶ Such a claim is supported by recent advances in quantum mechanics: even mathematics itself is now relying on speculative dialectical logic to make sense of the material structure of the world and our lives in it, as deductive logic obfuscates our observed ‘units of analysis’ from self-relating (Žižek, 2017). We continue such approaches because of the (phallic) enjoyment obtained in surplus, thus centering the necessity of psychoanalysis in revealing this enjoyment. This enjoyment is not based on an ethics of love, for such love²⁷ would require narcissistic sacrifice and letting go of some of our enjoyment: giving it up to engage in the Symbolic of the social link. I wager that we shall not have much choice in a few decades from now, when the ecological catastrophe reaches a critical point, and mass migration and widening global social class gaps render our research enterprise essentially meaningless.

Just as we (hopefully) teach our pre-service teachers that mathematics class doesn’t happen in a vacuum, so, too, do the dominant discourses of our field not happen in a vacuum. They are—despite researchers’ otherwise intentions—material interventions in the social-being and ideologies of the world.²⁸ This is what I mean by the need to “desire better”: desiring not for the self (or the market) but for the other. Mathematics education is damaged, and thus causes damage. We have no business in developing commercial flights to space whilst most of the world population does not have enough food, water, sanitation; mathematics education is and has always been complicit in this ethical failure. As mathematics education researchers, our duty is to now turn towards such approaches at large in the field.

Psychoanalyzing the Field

My editorial colleagues may disagree with my theoretical approach, and indeed that is one of our strengths: our perspectives are in places distinct to the point of mutual exclusivity, and yet they offer an opportunity for sociopolitical cohesion. For my part, I would not describe myself as a postmodernist because postmodern ideology rejects global narratives in favor of the local, thus disavowing the role of what Lacan would call master-signifiers (see Lacan, 1991/2007). Postmodernism is, thus, antithetical to the psychoanalytic-Marxist perspective. I believe that postmodernism is a promising future endeavor, but until we have addressed the inherent inequity with which the modern schooling system has been designed as its foundation, this postmodernist dream shall not have a chance; rather, it will only contribute to widening the gap between our work as researchers and the psychic and material realities of our research subjects. In this way, I am calling on the field to “go backwards” (i.e., self-reflect, un-do, un-make, search for the reasons for the symptoms) and consider the material inequity that forms the basis of our entire enterprise: the surplus-value of those who fail is seized by those who pass (Baldino & Cabral, 2013, 2015, 2018), as evidenced by the surplus-enjoyment (see Žižek, 2022) of passing and being successful in school and assimilating oneself into the market. This is the way that the capitalist mode of school is designed: to produce the next generation of capitalism’s useful idiots (see Andersen, 2021), with them having been ideologically indoctrinated to “live life to the fullest”—of course, in the capitalist

²⁶ I borrow this term from my friend Cameron More, who is another Lacanian scholar in my “cartel,” which is what Lacan called psychoanalytic study groups.

²⁷ This may be a triggering word to read in the context of mathematics education research, but consider who else’s role it might be to be obsessed with the use of love except that of a queer person (in my case, a gay man) whose license to love is systematically foreclosed by society. What else could this be, for me, other than a symptom?

²⁸ I teach my pre-service teacher students that “There is no content to teach; there are only people to teach.” I borrow this term from one of the sponsoring teachers with whom I have worked.

way. Failing to engage with the existential burden (Pais, 2022) this places on our research subjects will continue to sublimate researchers' insistence on the phantasy of an idealist mathematics education that doesn't exist.

Mathematics is and has always been political (Sohn-Rethel, 1978), and so, too, has school (Clarke, 2021); this means that the field of mathematics education is a political enterprise (Pais, 2011, 2016). The field's disavowal of this is, in short, the effect of ideology: it is the truth-kernel of the "disorder of mathematics education" today (see Andrade-Molina, this volume; Straehler-Pohl et al., 2017). We need more theoretical advances in ideology, dialectical materialism, and psychoanalysis *specifically in and for our field* (and widespread avowals of their importance) if we are to remain relevant in the coming decades (for an example in general educational theory, see Clarke, 2021; for some examples in mathematics education, see Brown, 2008, 2020)—moreover, these advances need to not be restricted to a certain subset of the field: they must be foundational parts of training the next generation of scholars, and in the current workforce of mathematics education researchers in reflecting on their own work's role in supporting the disorder of the field.²⁹ My rationale for this claim is simply that mathematics is an exceedingly peculiar educational content, psychically speaking (e.g., Moore, 2022) and materially speaking (e.g., Sohn-Rethel, 1978), which is perhaps why there are so many of us who, for half a century now, have devoted our lives to trying to understand it. Obviously, the strangeness of mathematics³⁰ and its education has captured the desire of many.³¹ However, this task of new intentional theoretical development—within the psychoanalytic-Marxist-dialectical way—shall no doubt be met with contrarian responses from the neoliberal universities in which we all work (see Andersen, 2021). Indeed, hysterical responses disavowing such an approach should be considered as symptoms, and thus investigated as to their Symbolic core (see Žižek, 1989/2008a). Investigating the 'whys' for the symptoms will lead to the traversal of the phantasies of the field, an exasperated expression of the phantasies which we each hold and which bind our enterprise together. This shall no doubt be a frightening proposition to undertake, but we encourage scholars to engage with such ideas in future submissions to the

²⁹ For example, I wager that Brown (2020) should be standard first-year reading for any university degree in mathematics education, including undergraduate degrees.

³⁰ What I have elsewhere (Moore, in press) called the *Ding*-ness of mathematics.

³¹ I would also say that, based on my interactions with other scholars around my age—I am currently 35 years old—or younger, there is an increasing sense of hopelessness for the future that has spurred many into action in critiquing and/or rejecting the political economy status-quo that my generation has inherited. As a result, this collective "weariness"—*qua* existential burden—"spurs [us] into action" (Pais, 2022, p. 84): my sense is that there is an increasing bifurcation along lines of banality in my generation, where some are very happy with banality (which I would align with Andersen's (2021) term of the "useful idiot") and some entirely reject it (e.g., the increasing polarization of politics and reemergence of fascist and communist thought today). I, of course, speak from the American perspective, and perhaps this is my critical/feminist/Marxist/queer/rural perspective overdetermining my interpretations of the world, but it is at least affirmed by an increasing number of interactions I have with other colleagues in the field. Žižek said once (I do not remember where, but it was in an interview) that the true Hegelian step for our time is to embrace the hopelessness which—by a dialectical interpretation—means that we must accept that fundamental changes must happen at the level of political economy, not along lines of revision, but of replacement—and we must be open to it. For me, this is why I always return to the level of Marxian analysis (i.e., the level of the master-signifier); I see other approaches as operating within the ideologies I wish to critique. I, of course, opine here: we must learn to "desire better"—to "get over" capital and curb our "fueling [of] the juggernaut" (Baldino & Cabral, 2018, p. 197) before we completely destroy ourselves and the world. As researchers, we have the ability to demand such changes at the policy level, if only we will accept that ethical duty with enthusiasm and resolve. I base this claim on the gap I see between our work and the persistent reality of school: our actions form the necessary support for this toxic system, the demands of which have already been delineated for us beforehand (Butler et al., 2000). This is precisely the mechanism of ideology today. Theory is important because it reflects our engagement with ideology; thus theoretical and ideological developments specifically *in and for our field* are needed if we are to change the direction of the juggernaut that guides us.

Journal. After all, “Education does not exist and Mathematics is its symptom” (Baldino & Cabral, 2018, p. 178).³²

A Possible (?) Conclusion: Join Us in the Margins

If you have come here to help me, you are wasting your time. But if you have come because your liberation is bound up with mine, then let us work together.

—Aboriginal Activist Group (ca. 1970’s), Queensland, Australia³³

We cannot overstate the enthusiastic reception this project (*JTM-ME*) has received in the field thus far. The casual conversations, the conference run-ins, the random emails, and so forth have shown us that the field is ready for this project. We can say with certainty that we have identified a gap—a need—in the field. We are encouraged by this warm reception and the enthusiastic responses we have already received. We formed *JTM-ME* as a way to establish a continuous presence for this type of work in the field, and it is by this continuous spirit that we solicit submissions for 2(1), to be published in late 2023. The call for submissions can be found at <https://jtm.cppei.me> and interested authors are encouraged to email the editorial office at jtm@cppei.me if there are any hesitations, concerns, questions, or uncertainties about submissions that you wish to prepare, or to discuss new forms or ideas that you may not be sure of their fit. As this is a communal/anarchist vanguard outlet, we want to work with you if you need interlocutors in developing your ideas or discussing ways forward for potential submissions. In this way, we see *JTM-ME* as being a social force for change. As Hegel said, we need new institutions. Well, yes, indeed—and here is one that we are proud to offer to the field.

About the Authors

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³² Here, I scand (break) my speech.

³³ This quote is often attributed solely to Lillia Watson, an Aboriginal activist who was heard by many when she shared it at the 1985 United Nations Decade for Women Conference. However, when asked about it, Lillia Watson has been clear in stating that she is not comfortable being given solo credit for something that was a collective process.

philosophers Michel Foucault and Jacques Rancière, his works operate at the level of power-knowledge and interrogate the norms and conditions that marginalize certain ideas and productions of knowledges within mathematics education research. His use of citation network ‘maps’ to identify clusters of research (available at [MathEdAtlas.org](https://www.mathedatlas.org)) illuminates normative assumptions about what constitutes mathematics education research *per se* while simultaneously giving substantial insight into the scope and direction of the field of mathematics education research writ large. He can be reached via email at dubbs@cppi.me or cdubbs@esu.edu.

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